

DEFORMATION AND RECRYSTALLIZATION BEHAVIOUR OF SiC PARTICULATE REINFORCED 6061 ALUMINIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The deformation and recrystallization behaviour of 6061 aluminium alloy reinforced with 20% SiC particulate composites have been investigated for two particulate sizes. It has been found that both higher strength and ductility were obtained at the smaller particle size. The microstructure following deformation to low strains (<10%) and annealing at 350°C for various lengths of time was studied by optical and transmission electron microscopy. The deformation microstructure was observed to be homogeneous, without the presence of deformation zones around the SiC particles. Furthermore, recrystallization nuclei were observed to form at grain boundaries, rather than in the matrix surrounding the SiC particles.

Keywords: aluminium, recrystallization, metal matrix composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminium-based metal matrix composites (MMC) are envisaged as candidate structural materials for the aerospace and automotive industries because of their low density, high stiffness, and high tensile and compressive strengths [1]. MMCs containing discontinuous particulate reinforcement are especially attractive because their properties are more isotropic than either whisker or fibre reinforcement. The near isotropic properties of particulate reinforced MMCs means that they can be shaped by conventional secondary metal-working techniques. During such forming operations the MMCs may experience appreciable amounts of cold work, which may degrade some mechanical properties, such as elongation to failure and fatigue resistance. Therefore, after some forming operations it may be necessary to anneal the composite. Recent studies [2-10] have examined the recrystallization behaviour of MMCs by thermal annealing after large amounts of cold working (30-90% reductions). These studies report that the reinforcing particles have a significant influence on the recrystallization behaviour of the matrix alloy: the recrystallization rate of MMCs is usually faster than in the equivalent unreinforced alloy. For example, Shahani and Clyne [4] studied the recovery and recrystallization of commercially pure aluminium containing either SiC, Al₂O₃ or saffil which was cold worked to a total reduction of 53%. They found that the recrystallization temperature was lower for the composites (between 300 and

350°C) than for the unreinforced aluminium (460°C). Humphreys [2] reported that the recrystallization temperature is dependent on both the size and volume fraction of the particulates, most rapid recrystallization occurring in composites with the smallest particles and largest volume fractions. In addition, the size of the recrystallized grains was found to decrease with decreasing particle size and increase with decreasing particle volume fraction.

While the above studies have examined the recrystallization behaviour of MMCs deformed by large amounts of cold working, very little work has been done on recrystallization at lower amounts (i. e. <10% reduction) of deformation. The work presented in this paper was carried out to obtain a better understanding of the effect of small amounts of deformation in compression on the recovery and recrystallization behaviour of MMCs, in two aluminium-based composites reinforced with either 3 μm or 20 μm diameter SiC particulates.

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES AND MATERIALS

The materials used in this study were the aluminium alloy 6061 reinforced with (a) 3 μm SiC particulates (referred to in this paper as composite A) and (b) 20 μm SiC particulates (composite B). Both composites had a SiC volume fraction (V_f) of 20%. The materials were manufactured by Comalco Research Centre (Victoria, Australia), and were processed by a powder metallurgy route [11], then hot extruded into rods. After processing the materials were heat treated to the T6 condition, i. e. solution treatment at 530°C for 1.5 h, quenched in cold water, aged at room temperature for 20 h, and then artificially aged at 175°C for 8 h. The unreinforced 6061 alloy, obtained from Comalco, was also investigated and given similar T6 treatment as the composites.

Mechanical properties (i. e. yield strength, UTS and Young's Modulus) of the materials were determined by tensile testing at room temperature. The specimens for the tensile tests were cylindrical in shape, with gauge diameter of 6 mm and gauge length of 25 mm (ASTM Standard E8). These specimens were tested using an Instron Machine (Type 1185) at a strain rate of $8.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The uniaxial compression deformation was performed using cylindrical specimens with diameter of 13 mm and length of 25 mm, compressed at a strain rate of $8.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to a strain of either 6% or 9%. The specimens were deformed parallel to their original extrusion direction. After being plastically deformed in compression, specimens were isothermally annealed at 350°C for 1, 2, 5, 10, 50, 100 and 200 minutes (60, 120, 300, 600, 3000, 6000 and 12000 seconds), then immediately water quenched.

The deformed and recrystallized microstructures were studied by both optical and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Specimens for these studies were sliced parallel to the compression axis. Thin foils for TEM were jet polished to perforation using a 20% nitric acid and 80% methanol solution at a potential of 20V at a temperature of -25°C. The foils were examined in a JEOL 2000FX TEM.

In this paper the recrystallization behaviour of composite A will be presented, and experiments are continuing for composite B.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Original Microstructure

Fig. 1 presents the microstructure of the two composites in the T6 condition. The grain sizes of

the matrices of both composites were found to be non-uniform. The average grain size was measured to be about 4 μm in composite A and 7 μm in composite B. However, Fig. 1 shows some depletion and clustering of the SiC particles. A typical zone depleted in SiC is shown in composite A (labelled "X" in Fig. 1a), the aluminium grain size within this zone was about 15 μm . Regions of SiC clustering (labelled "Y" in Fig. 1b) contained very small aluminium grains, usually less than 2 μm in diameter. Similar behaviour was observed in composite B. These measurements show that the SiC particle size influences the aluminium grain size during the thermomechanical processing of composites. This is consistent with the studies of Ferry et al. who recently observed that clusters of reinforcing particles strongly inhibited grain growth during annealing of a 2014/Al₂O₃ MMC at 500°C [12].

3.2. Mechanical Properties

Table 1 lists the mechanical properties measured for the unreinforced alloy and the two composites in T6 condition. Clearly, the SiC particles increased both the UTS and Young's Modulus, but also reduced ductility. It is interesting to note that composite A has slightly different mechanical properties compared to composite B.

Table 1 Tensile Properties for Materials in T6 Condition

Material	Young's Modulus(E) (GPa)*	Yield Strength (MPa)*	Ultimate Strength (MPa)#	Elongation (in 25 mm) (%)#
6061 Alloy	65.2	250	264	15.3
Composite A	96.2	338	378	6.7
Composite B	102.6	320	344	5.7

Note: Three specimens used for (*) and one specimen used for (#)

According to McDanel [13] and Nair et al. [14] the mechanical properties of particulate reinforced composites closely follow the rule of mixture, and are therefore linearly dependent on the volume fraction of reinforcement but independent of particle size. Since composites A and B have the same volume fraction of SiC particles (20%), but different particle sizes, it would be expected from the rule of mixture that these composites should have the same properties. However, Table 1 shows that the yield and ultimate tensile strengths are lower in composite B, indicating that the rule of mixture does not necessarily work for these composites and the SiC particle size appears to influence the mechanical properties. The finer grain size in composite A may strengthen this material with respect to composite B through Hall-Petch considerations. Furthermore, Arsenault et al. have shown that for a fixed volume fraction of reinforcement, yield strength increases as the particle size decreases due to an increase in dislocation density [15], and the present observations are consistent with that finding.

Fracture surfaces of the tensile specimens are shown in Fig. 2. The surface of the unreinforced aluminium showed uniform deformation and dimple size (Fig. 2a). The surface of composite A (Fig. 2b) is similar to that of the unreinforced aluminium, which are small dimples with very few SiC particles exposed. These observations suggest that in composite A the fracture largely occurred in the aluminium matrix. In contrast, the fracture of composite B (Fig. 2c) was not uniform; large dimples were observed around the SiC particles and small dimples in the

aluminium matrix away from the particles. This surface also contained a large number of broken SiC particles. These observations indicate that this composite fails by a mixture of ductile failure in the aluminium matrix and brittle fracture of the SiC particles.

3.3. Recovery and Recrystallization Behaviour

Fig. 3 shows optical and TEM micrographs of composite A after compression to a strain of 6%. It is seen in Fig. 3a that under compression the aluminium grains were elongated along the axis normal to the loading direction. Fig. 3b shows a TEM micrograph of composite A where a homogeneous array of dislocation tangles can be observed. Similar observations were made for 9% deformation. Increased deformation in the vicinity of the SiC particles, commonly observed following large strains, was not observed here.

The recrystallization behaviour of composite A compressed to 6% and 9% strains at 350°C was monitored by measuring the change in Vickers macrohardness (at a load of 5 kg) with annealing time. The initial hardness after 6% and 9% compression are 123 HV and 141 HV respectively (see Fig. 4). The hardness is seen to decrease slightly with increasing annealing time up to 60 seconds, after which it decreased rapidly to about 75 HV in ~600 seconds. It is interesting to note that the rate of softening between times of 60 and 600 seconds is approximately the same for the composite compressed to 6% and 9%. This suggests that the recovery rate was independent of the amount of cold work, at these low strains.

Fig. 5a shows the TEM micrographs of the matrix grains in composite A after being annealed for 300 seconds. It is seen that there has been a significant reduction in the dislocation density, and cell formation has occurred. Ferry et al. [7] examined annealing of a 2014 aluminium alloy containing Al₂O₃ particles compressed to 30 and 50% reduction. They found that the microstructure close to the Al₂O₃ particles recovered more rapidly than in the areas devoid of these particles. This was attributed to deformation zones that formed around the particles in the heavily cold worked composites. In this study, the TEM examination of composite A failed to reveal the preferential recovery of the microstructure close to SiC particles. Clearly, the low level of deformation in the alloys studied here, compared with the work of Ferry et al., resulted in the absence of well developed deformation zones around the particulates.

Fig. 5b shows that after annealing for 600 seconds, small grains began to form within the large, deformed aluminium grains. These small grains exhibited low angle boundaries with the deformed grains, suggesting that they were subgrains. Humphreys [2,3] and Ferry et al. [7] reported that during annealing the growth of subgrains may be impeded by the reinforcing particles pinning the subgrain boundaries. Humphreys [3] found that in aluminium-based composites, subgrain pinning occurs when $V_f/d > 0.1$, where V_f is the volume fraction of particulates and d is the particulate diameter. The ratio V_f/d for composites A and B is equal to 0.066 and 0.010 μm^{-1} (assuming the size of particulates to be the same as the diameter), indicating that the SiC particles do not impede the subgrain growth process. It appears, therefore, that the rapid reduction in hardness of the composite shown in Fig. 5 is caused by recovery of many of the dislocation forests within the deformed aluminium, together with some subgrain growth.

It was seen in Fig. 4 that at times greater than ~600 seconds the rate of drop in hardness significantly slows down with annealing time. TEM observations revealed that recrystallized grains begin to form within the aluminium matrix during this stage of annealing, as shown in Fig. 6 for composite A compressed to 9% (6a) and 6% (6b). These figures show that the recrystallized grains nucleated at prior high-angle boundaries of the deformed grains. The

recrystallized grains did not appear to nucleate along the boundary between the SiC particles and deformed aluminium. In contrast, other studies [2, 4, 7] have found that recrystallized grains usually nucleate in heavily deformed zones around the particulates. It appears, therefore, that in composites which have been lightly cold worked, the recrystallized grain will nucleate at the grain boundaries rather than at the reinforcing particles.

While the recrystallization of the aluminium occurred at about the same time for the compression of 6% and 9% (Fig. 4), it was found by TEM that the nucleation density of recrystallized grains was higher in the specimen deformed to 9%. A similar observation has been reported by Shahani and Clyne [4], who found that the critical nucleation size of recrystallized grains was reduced with increasing the amount of cold working. Furthermore, TEM examination of the composites after annealing for 3000 seconds revealed a considerable amount of growth in the recrystallized grains in the specimen compressed to 9% while the grain growth was significantly less in the specimen compressed to 6%.

The above results show that annealing of the composite occurs in two stages: firstly, the dislocation forests are annihilated together with some subgrain growth, and this is followed by the nucleation and growth of recrystallized grains from the boundaries of the deformed grains.

4. CONCLUSIONS

(1) For the same matrix and same volume fraction of reinforcements, decreasing the particle size will slightly increase the tensile strength and ductility of 6061 with SiC reinforced composites.

(2) At low strain (<10%) deformation, the deformation microstructure in composite A is relatively homogeneous.

(3) At low strain (<10%) deformation, the grain boundary region is the dominating site for nucleation of recrystallization.

References

1. Ibrahim, I.A., Mohamed, F.A. and Lavernia, E.J., *Particulate Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites - a Review*, J. Mat. Sci., 26, 1991, pp. 1137.
2. Humphreys, F.J., *Particle Stimulated Nucleation of Recrystallization*, Recrystallization '90, edited by Chandra, T., TMS, Warrendale, PA, 1990, pp. 113.
3. Humphreys, F.J., *The Thermomechanical Processing of Al-SiC Particulate Composites*, Mat. Sci. Eng., A135, 1991, pp. 267.
4. Shahani, R.A., Clyne, T.M., *Recrystallization in Fibrous and Particulate Metal Matrix Composites*, Mat. Sci. Eng., A135, 1991, pp. 285.
5. Humphreys, F.J., Miller, W.S., and Djazeb, M.R., *Microstructural Development During Thermomechanical Processing of Particulate Metal-Matrix Composites*, Mat. Sci. Tech., 6, 1990, pp. 1157.
6. Ferry, M., Munroe, P.R., Crosky, A., and Chandra, T., *A Study of the Recrystallization Behaviour of a Deformed Aluminium Composite Reinforced with Alumina Particles*, Pro. 12th Riso Symp. on "Metal Matrix Composites: Processing, Microstructure and Properties", edited by N. Hansen et al. Roskilde Denmark, Riso National Laboratory, 1991, pp. 337.
7. Ferry, M., Munroe, P.R., Crosky, A. and Chandra, T., *Microstructural Development During Cold Deformation and Recrystallization of 2014 Al-Al₂O₃ Particulate Composites*, Mat. Sci. Tech., Jan. 1992, Vol. 8, pp. 43.
8. Munroe, P.R., Ferry, M., *Microstructural Development of 2014 Al-Al₂O₃ MMC Following*

Cold Work and Subsequent Isochronal Annealing, Proc. 2nd Australian Forum on MMCs, edited by Bandyopadhyay, S. and Crosky, A.G., University of NSW, 1992, pp. 13.

9. Liu, Y.L., Hansen, N., and Jensen, D.J., *Recrystallization Microstructure in Cold-Rolled Aluminium Composites Reinforced by Silicon Carbide Whiskers*, Met. Trans, 20A, 1989, pp. 1743.

10. Liu, Y.L., Hansen, N., and Jensen, D.J., *Effect of Dispersion Parameters and Cold Deformation on Recrystallization of Al-SiC Composites*, Mat. Sci. Tech., 7, 1991, pp. 270.

11. Couper, M.J., Setargew, N., Clayton, A.H.A., Tarr, R. and Bandyopadhyay, S., *Preliminary Characterisation of Silicon Carbide and Alumina Reinforced Aluminium Metal Matrix Composites*, Proc. of Materials Unites in the Service of Man, edited by Davies, R.D. and Hatcher, D.I., Perth, Australia, pp. 1.

12. Ferry, M., Munroe, P.R., Crosky, A., *Grain Growth of an Aluminium 2014/Al₂O₃ PMMC During Solution Heat Treatment*, Scripta Metall., (in press), 1993.

13. McDanel, D.L., *Analysis of Stress-strain, Fracture, and Ductility Behaviour of Al Matrix Composites Discontinuous SiC Reinforcement*, Metall. Trans., 16A, Jun. 1985, pp. 1105.

14. Nair, S.V., Tien, J.K., Bates, R.C., *SiC Reinforced Metal Matrix Composite*, Int. Met. Rev., 30, 1985, pp. 257.

15. Arsenault, R.J., Wang, L. and Feng, C.R., *Strengthening of Composites Due to Microstructural Changes in the Matrix*, Acta Metall., Vol. 39, No. 1, 1991, pp. 47.

Figure 1. Optical micrographs showing the microstructure of (a) composite A and (b) composite B in T6 condition (Transverse direction)

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of tensile fracture surfaces
(a) 6061 unreinforced alloy
(b) composite A
(c) composite B

Figure 3. (a) Optical and (b) TEM micrographs showing the microstructure of composite A following 6 % strain in compression

Figure 4. Vickers' hardness (Load 5kg) vs time at 350°C for composite A

Figure 5. TEM micrographs showing recovery in composite A following 6% strain in compression (a) 350°C after 300 sec. and (b) 350°C after 600 sec.

Figure 6. TEM micrographs showing recrystallization nuclei in composite A at 350°C (a) 9% strain, after 6×10^3 sec. and (b) 6% strain, after 3×10^3 sec.